

A hardware-aware neural architecture search algorithm for wearable robotics

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Abstract—Hardware-aware neural architecture search (HW NAS), the process of automating the design of neural architectures taking into consideration hardware constraints, has already outperformed the best human designs on many tasks. However, it is known to be highly demanding in terms of hardware, thus limiting access to non-habitual neural network users. Fostering its adoption for the next-generation wearable robotic devices design, we propose an HW NAS that can be run on laptops, even if not mounting a GPU. The proposed technique, designed to have both a low search cost and resource usage, produces tiny convolutional neural networks (CNNs) targeting low-end microcontrollers, typically applied in developing wearable robotic devices. Such CNNs can be used to analyse multiple sEMG or force signals, like in the force myography use case, to control wearable robotic devices without the need for costly and powerful hardware specifically designed to run CNNs on the edge. It achieves state-of-the-art results in the human-recognition tasks, on the Visual Wake Word dataset a standard TinyML benchmark, in just 3:37:0 hours on a laptop mounting an 11th Gen Intel(R) Core(TM) i7-11370H CPU @ 3.30GHz equipped with 16 GB of RAM and 512 GB of SSD, without using a GPU.

Index Terms—Wearable Robotics, Hardware Aware Neural Architecture Search, TinyML, Convolutional Neural Networks, Microcontrollers

I. INTRODUCTION

The outstanding success of convolutional neural networks (CNNs) for image classification has been supported by the increasing amount of computational power offered by GPUs. Indeed, in the recent years researchers have tried to reproduce such results on devices with limited computational complexity. Manually designed CNNs for mobile devices like Mobilenets [1], Shufflenets [2], and EfficientNets [3] have surged. Based on such efforts, projects like Mnasnet [4] and Fbnet [5] have tried to automatize the process of designing CNNs for custom tasks, given different hardware targets. These techniques gave birth to Hardware-aware neural architecture search (HW NAS).

Several NAS exploits reinforcement learning to search for the best architecture under the constraints imposed by the target device. A controller produces instances of architectures and is rewarded based on the accuracy obtained and the hardware cost. This is the case of MNASNet [4], FPNNet [6], Codesign-NAS [7], and [8]. This approach often implies a training phase for each architecture generated. These

techniques usually requires about thousands of GPU days of searching/training to achieve state-of-the-art computer vision results.

Such issue has been addressed in then literature by introducing an over-parametrized network, known as supernet; it contains all the models belonging to the search space as sub-networks, which share weights. Such a solution allows training only one big network and then searching inside it for the best sub-network, thus reducing the search time. Techniques like evolutionary algorithms [9] [10] [11] and gradient descent methods [5] [12] [13] [14] [15] are commonly used to search for the best sub-network. Even if the search time has been drastically reduced, a super network still requires high-end GPUs to be trained.

The present research introduces a novel approach to HW NAS that limits both search time and resource usage. The low resource usage is guaranteed by the constrains imposed on the target, which lead to regular architectures with small footprints. The low search cost is achieved by adopting a novel derivative-free search strategy proposed in this paper, which explores minimal-footprint solutions suitable for low-end microcontrollers, typically used in the development of wearable robotic devices. Such CNNs can be applied for the analysis of multiple sEMG signals or force sensors, like in the force myography use case, to control wearable robotic devices without the need for costly and powerful hardware, specifically designed to run CNNs on the edge.

The proposed HW NAS achieved state-of-the-art results in the human-recognition tasks on the Visual Wake Word dataset [16] a standard benchmark for TinyML [17]. The search time was 3:37:0 hours on a laptop with an 11th Gen Intel(R) Core(TM) i7-11370H CPU @ 3.30GHz, 16 GB of RAM, and 512 GB of SSD; the GPU was not involved in the search process. The models and the code proposed in this document can be downloaded at <https://github.com/AndreaMattiaGaravagno/NanoNAS>.

The present research has already been published in the proceedings of the 18th Conference on Ph.D Research in Microelectronics and Electronics (PRIME) held in Valencia, Spain, on June 18-21 2023 [18]. It is re-proposed with a view to scientific dissemination, aiming to foster the usage of deep learning in wearable robotic devices.

II. PROPOSED HARDWARE-AWARE NEURAL ARCHITECTURE SEARCH

Every HW NAS technique has three hallmarks: the search space, the formulation of the optimization problem, and the search strategy. The search space defines the rules and set of network's architectural elements that will be used to build the candidate solutions. The optimization problem establishes the search boundaries and the metric adopted to evaluate each candidate. Finally, the search strategy describes how the search space is explored, i.e., how the solution is found.

A. Search Space

There are three types of search spaces: layer-wise, cell-wise and hierarchical. Our solution adopts a cell-wise search space. It builds a candidate solution by staking cells composed of fixed architectural elements, as can be seen in figure 1. The cell (yellow dashed line in the figure) has three layers: a 2-dimensional max pooling layer followed by a batch normalization layer which feeds a convolutional layer. Every max pooling layer halves the input resolution using a 2x2 receptive field with (2,2) stride. Convolutional layers use (3,3) kernels with (1,1) stride and ReLu activation.

The cells are stacked upon a fixed structure which includes a pre-processing pipeline (green dashed line in the figure) and the first convolutional layer (red dashed line in the Figure). The pre-processing pipeline performs min-max standardization and batch normalization on the input data. The number of kernels, k , used in the first convolutional layer sets the number of kernels used in the following cells according to (1). Equation (1) is inspired by the procedure used in the VGG16 [19] architecture, where a cell doubles the number of kernels with respect to the previous cell. However, in the proposed approach this amplification is modulated cell after cell, to limit the parameters' growth.

$$n_c = \begin{cases} k & \text{if } c = 0 \\ \left\lceil \left(2 - \sum_{i=1}^{c-1} 2^{-i}\right) \cdot n_{c-1} \right\rceil & \text{if } c \geq 1 \end{cases} \quad (1)$$

The output of the last cell is then reduced by a global average pooling layer followed by a dropout layer which feeds a final layer having softmax activation and a number of neurons equal to the number of classes to be classified (gray dashed line in the figure).

Thus, candidate solutions are built by stacking c cells upon a fixed basis. A candidate solution can be conveniently described by two parameters k and c . Parameter k defines the number of kernels used in the first convolutional layer while c defines the number of cells.

This solution creates a small search space that typically includes a few thousand possible samples, which can lessen to a few hundred in cases of really tight resource constraints. Techniques which includes typically few thousand samples in the search space are classified as NAS according to the review paper [20].

Fig. 1. Graphical representation of a generic element belonging to the search space, characterized by k kernels in the first convolutional layer and c cells.

B. Problem Formulation

HW NAS aims to find the best neural architecture for the target hardware in the search space. This translates into a constrained optimization problem where the objective function describes the metric adopted to evaluate candidate solutions and the constraints set the boundaries of the search. In the proposed problem formulation, candidates are evaluated by training them for three epochs and applying validation-based early stopping [21], i.e., we sample the maximum validation accuracy obtained in the first three epochs of training. The boundaries of the search are upper limited by the available amount of RAM and Flash, and by the number of multiply and accumulate (MACC) operations, which represents a proxy

for the latency as suggested by Micronets [13].

$$P1 : \begin{cases} \max f(x) \\ \phi_R(x) \leq \xi_R \\ \phi_F(x) \leq \xi_F \\ \phi_M(x) \leq \xi_M \\ \xi_R, \xi_F, \xi_M > 0 \end{cases} \quad (2)$$

This leads to the problem formulation presented in equation (2), where function f returns the maximum validation accuracy obtained during training; function ϕ_R the network’s peak RAM occupancy; function ϕ_F the network’s Flash occupancy; function ϕ_M the network’s number of MACC. These depend on the number of kernels used in the first layer k , the number of cells added c , and the magnitude of the network’s input size s . The latter is omitted in the formulation since it is considered fixed during the search, hence the search variable $x = (k, c)$ is defined. $f(x)$ values come from training.

C. Search Strategy

The optimization problem P is solved with a derivative-free optimization technique, as function f is not differentiable. The algorithm used is inspired by the principle of parsimony, known as Occam’s razor, which states that entities should not be multiplied beyond necessity.

Algorithm 1 formalizes the search strategy, which starts from scratch with the lowest admissible number of kernels in the first layer, i.e., $k = 1$. Two loops drive the search strategy. The outer loop increments k , while the inner loop increments c . In both cases, the increment progresses if the generalization capability, $f(k, c)$, increases and the constraints set in (2) hold, i.e., (k, c) is feasible. The algorithm’s output is the neural architecture with the best score among those explored.

Such a strategy limits the parameters growth, adding resources only when needed. For this reason, MACC, RAM and Flash occupancy are not explicitly included in the objective function f .

Algorithm 1 search strategy pseudocode

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 $k \leftarrow 1$       ▷ Minimum number of kernels of the first layer
 $c \leftarrow 0$     ▷ No cells added
while  $(k, c)$  is feasible and  $f(k, c)$  increases do
   $c \leftarrow 0$       ▷ Reset cells
  while  $(k, c)$  is feasible and  $f(k, c)$  increases do
     $c \leftarrow c + 1$   ▷ Try with one more cell
  end while
   $k \leftarrow k + 1$   ▷ Try with more kernels
end while
return  $(k, c) : \max f(k, c)$ 

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III. EXPERIMENTS

The proposed HW NAS has been evaluated on the Visual Wake Word dataset [16], a standard TinyML benchmark [17], useful to compare the proposed work with the state-of-the-art. The Visual Wake Word dataset contains around 123k images

identifying whether a person is present in the image or not. The datasets provide fixed training and testing splits.

The HW NAS has been run on the largest among the lightest target architectures used by MCUNet [9] and Micronets [13] projects given that their target are high-performance microcontrollers, while low-end microcontrollers represent the actual target of the present research. An input size of $(50, 50, 3)$, a batch size of 16, a learning rate of 0.001 and the Adam optimizer [22] have been used. The resulting architecture has been trained with a batch size of 128 and a learning rate of 0.01 for 100 epochs. In both cases, 10% of the training data has been reserved for validation. Finally, 8-bit post training quantization has been applied. The trained CNN obtained a test accuracy score of 77% with a recall of 0.681 and an F1-score of 0.736. The total execution time was 3 hours and 37 minutes. It includes the search cost plus the final training.

Figure 2 summarizes the comparison. It contains four bar plots, one for each quantity taken into consideration: Test accuracy, Flash occupancy, RAM occupancy and MACC. As recall and F1-score were not reported in [9] [13], such quantities are not involved in the figure. Each plot compares the performance of MCUNet, Micronets and the CNN selected by the HW NAS.

Fig. 2. State-of-the-art comparison on the Visual Wake Word dataset, a standard benchmark for TinyML applications. The lightest neural architecture proposed by MCUNet [9] and Micronets [13] projects, namely “mcunet-vww0”⁶ and “MicroNet VWW-2 INT8”⁷, are taken into account. Both ROM and RAM occupancy have been computed thanks to the TFLite Micro API.

The obtained CNN achieves a test accuracy slightly higher than Micronets [13] but lower than MCUNet [9], as shown in figure 2. However, it is the only architecture that fits the tight resource constraints of the ultra-low-power NUCLEO-

L412KB board by ST Microelectronics, i.e. 128 kBytes of Flash and 40 kBytes of RAM.

IV. CONCLUSION

To the best of our knowledge, this is the first HW NAS to not require GPUs at all to obtain results in a reasonable execution time. Such a characteristic can help those designers who want to start using HW NAS in their applications, democratizing its usage. The reduced resource requirements of the resulting CNNs make the algorithm particularly suitable for low-end microcontrollers.

Authors believe that these features can interest the research community involved in the design of wearable robotics, providing an easy way to use deep learning for the control of such devices based on the analysis of multiple sEMG or force signals, as in the force myography use case, in real-time, without the need for specific skills and costly and powerful hardware specifically designed to run deep learning on the edge.

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⁶<https://github.com/mit-han-lab/mcnunet> (accessed: 31.08.2023)

⁷https://github.com/ARM-software/ML-zoo/tree/master/models/visual_wake_words/micronet_vww2/flite_int8 (accessed: 31.08.2023)